

TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY GROWTH OF GRAM IN CHHATTISGARH

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Abstract

Increasing agricultural output is essential for the growth and food security of developing countries like India, where agriculture is the main stay of the economy. The country cannot depend too much upon new and growing supplies of inputs, therefore, the country will have to depend heavily upon improvements in the productive efficiency of factor inputs for future agricultural growth. The present study was undertaken to evaluate performance of gram in Chhattisgarh state over the period from 2002-03 to 2017-18 to examine the total factor productivity (TFP) growth. Total factor productivity was estimated using Tronquist Theil index. The results revealed that the less output produced as compared to input use in gram during overall period. Declining pattern observed in indices implies that all the inputs were not efficiently used in gram production during overall period in the region. The TFP of gram indicated an increasing trend during overall period in the region over all growth of Input Index, Out put index and TFP was 0.67 per cent, 1.27 per cent and 4.66 per cent respectively

Key word : Total Factor productivity, Gram, Chhattisgarh, Growth,

Introduction

The productivity growth in agriculture is both a necessary and sufficient condition for the development of the sector as well as the economy. It is a necessary condition in the sense that it enables agriculture to avoid a trap in to Ricardo's law of diminishing returns to which the sector is more prone. Productivity growth in agriculture is of paramount importance as higher yields are associated with declining rural poverty, suggesting that impact of growth in agricultural production on poverty remains high (Coelli al., 2005). The agricultural productivity continues to be an important driver of rural poverty reduction; especially it helps rise agricultural wages. The slow agricultural growth could be due to reduced demand for food, slow technological change in agriculture, lack of employment opportunities for part time smallholders, limited technology adoption by full-time farmers (Sharma, 2016).

Methodology**Selection of the study area and crop**

Chhattisgarh state was purposely selected for the Study and Gram crop selected for the study on the basis of highest acreage (290.66 thousand hectare) cover under pulses in Chhattisgarh state, as per the economics survey of Chhattisgarh 2017-18.

Period of study

The time-series secondary data for area and use of major agro-inputs were collected for calculation of total factor productivity and its findings is time period between 2002-03 to 2017-18 period of 16 year for the study

Collection of data

The crop wise data concerned to the area, production and productivity of chhattisgarh states from the time period of 2002-03 to 2017-18 was collected from various statistical year books published by the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Department of Agriculture, Government of India, and Co-operation and Farmers Welfare, farm input wholesale price index, GOI (<http://eands.dacnet.nic.in/>).

The analysis of TFP indices required data on the quantity and prices of the various inputs, i.e. seed, manure, fertilizer, human labour, machine labour, animal labour, insecticide, irrigation charges, land and output (main product and by-product). These data were collected for the period of 2002-03 to 2017-18 from the above- mentioned website and CACP data available on the Directorate of Economics and Statistics on Cost of Cultivation of Principal Crop in India.

Concept uses

Data on quantity and prices of these subsequent variables were collected for the estimation of total factor productivity.

Output: The total value of the output of the crop was derived by summing up the value of the main product and the by-product in rupees.

Input Input were collected in quantity per/h and there price per unit the calculation of TFP.

Human labour (in hours): The family and hired labour included. (Family labour means labour supplied by the family members for farming

purposes and hired labour means the labour supplied by the attached labour to the firm and the casual labourers on daily wages basis).

Animal labour (in hours): This comprised of the owned as well as hired animal labour.

Machine hours

Seeds (in Kg.)

Fertilizers (in Kg.)

Farm yard manure (FYM) (in quintals)

Insecticide (real price)

Irrigation machine hours

Source of data are:

Directorate of agricultural cooperation and farmer's welfare, Ministry of agriculture and farmer's welfare, GOI.

FCCI (2017) Indian maize summit report NCDEX

Agricultural statistics at a glance, GOI (Government of India)(2017)

Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperation, New Delhi.

Cost of Cultivation Principal Crops in India published yearly by Ministry of Agriculture

Analytical tools**Total factor productivity**

Total factor productivity is defined as the ratio of an index of aggregate output to an index of aggregate input. TFP implies an index of output per unit of total factor inputs and measures shifts in output holding all inputs constant (Throat *et al.*, 2006). The total factor productivity considered all the factors of production. It is also known as multifactor productivity. Laspeyres' arithmetic indices and Tronquist-Divisia Theil Index or Translog index are both used to measure total factor productivity in different studies. However, recent studies in the country on total factor productivity (Nishimizu 1982; Das *et.al* 2016) have employed the Tronquist-Divisia Theil Index or Translog index due to their superiority.

Total Output Index (TOI)

Output index construction for crop of the States was taken into account and per-unit price was considered for the conversion of physical values into monetary values. To evaluate the value of main product and by-product (kg/ha) of rice crop for all the years were collected and multiplied with the respective monetary value (price per unit) to get the value of the production. All these added to obtain the total value of production. The aggregated values of each year were taken to construct an output index using the Tornqvist chain-linked

index (Headey *et al.* 2010). The total output index was calculated using the following formula:

Tronquist Output Index (TAOI):

Tronquist output indices are constructed using the following formula:

$$TOI = \frac{TOI_{jt}}{TOI_{jt-1}} = \pi_j \left(\frac{Q_{jt}}{Q_{jt-1}} \right)^{(R_{jt}+R_{jt-1})/2}$$

where,

TOI_{jt} = Total output index of j^{th} crop in t^{th} period

TOI_{jt-1} = Total output index of j^{th} crop in $t^{th} - 1$ period

Q_{jt} = output of j^{th} crop in t^{th} period

Q_{jt-1} = output of j^{th} crop in $t^{th} - 1$ period

R_{jt} = output share of j^{th} crop in total revenue in t^{th} period

R_{jt-1} = output share of j^{th} crop in total revenue in $t^{th} - 1$ period

R_{jt} is calculated as follows

R_{jt} = value of j^{th} crop output in t^{th} period / Aggregate crop output value in t^{th} period

$$R_{jt} = \frac{Q_{jt}P_{jt}}{\sum Q_{jt}P_{jt}} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where,

Q_{jt} = output of j^{th} crop in t^{th} period

P_{jt} = Farm harvest price of j^{th} crop in t^{th} period

Total Inputs Index (TII)

Tronquist Input Indices are constructed using the following formula

$$TII = \frac{TII_{it}}{TII_{it-1}} = \pi_i \left(\frac{X_{it}}{X_{it-1}} \right)^{(S_{it}+S_{it-1})/2}$$

Where,

TII_{it} = Total input index of i^{th} input in t^{th} period

TII_{it-1} = Total input index of i^{th} input in $t^{th} - 1$ period

X_{it} = Quantity of i^{th} input used in j^{th} crop in t^{th} period

X_{it-1} = Quantity of i^{th} input used in j^{th} crop in $t^{th}-1$ period

S_{it} = Quantity of i^{th} input in t^{th} period / Total input cost in t^{th} period

$$S_{it} = \frac{X_{it}P_{it}}{\sum X_{it}P_{it}} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

where,

X_{it} = quantity of i^{th} input used in j^{th} crop in t^{th} period

P_{it} = Farm harvest price of i^{th} input of j^{th} crop in t^{th} period

The time series data on use of inputs and their prices in state of Chhattisgarh available under the comprehensive scheme for the study of Cost of Cultivation. Government of India (GOI) have been used in the analysis. The data on crop inputs included seed (kg/ha), manure (q/ha), fertilizer (kg/ha), human labour (hour/ha), animal labour (hour/ha), machine labour (Rs/ha),

insecticide (Rs./ha), irrigation (Rs./ha) and land revenue (Rs./ha).

Total factor productivity (TFP)

Total factor productivity indices are constructed as the ratio of total output index to total input index.

$$TFP_t = \frac{TOI_t}{TII_t}$$

where,

TFP_t = Total factor productivity index in t^{th} period

TII_t = Total input index in t^{th} period

TOI_t = Total output index in t^{th} period

Compound annual growth rate (CGAR) of Total Factor Productivity of gram in Chhattisgarh state

Compound growth rates were estimated with the following exponential model using least square techniques which are given below:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where,

Y = Trend value of dependent variable (area/ total production/yield)

a = constant

b = Trend coefficient (slope of line)

t = time variable (Years)

The function takes the form of a linear equation in logarithmic and becomes log-linear as under:

$$\log Y = \log a + \log b$$

$$\text{Compound growth rate (CGR)} = (\text{Antilog } \beta - 1) \times 100$$

CGR was estimated by applying OLS method. The t-test was performed to test the significance of β

Result and discussion

Average use of inputs and its Growth per hectare during 2002-03 to 2017-18

In the case of gram cultivation, the average seed usage was 82.53 kg, and 39.63 kg of fertilizer (nutrients) were applied. No manure was used, and human labor accounted for 245.43 man hours. Animal labor contributed 34.94 pair hours, while machines were utilized for 7.24 hours. Irrigation machines were used for 16.98 hours, and insecticides were applied at an average of 450.00 (real price)

CAGR of gram input during 2002-03 to 2017-18 reveals that the seed quantity growth was -0.58%, Fertilizer 8.51%, while manure remained constant at 0.0. Human labor hours had a slight decrease of -0.75%. Animal labor was experienced a significant decline of -18.94%. Machine usage has significant increased by 7.54%, while irrigation machine usage had a substantial growth rate of 34.26%. use of insecticide for gram has increased by 35.78% during this period and seed animal labour, machine and insecticide was found significant at 1% probability.

Table 1. Average use of inputs and its Growth per hectare during 2002-03 to 2017-18

inputs	Average	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	CGR %
Seed (Kg.)	82.53	0.262	0.040	6.482	0.0001	-0.58*
Fertilizer (Kg. Nutrients)	39.63	0.437	0.065	6.757	9.212	8.51
Manure (Qtl.)	0.00	0	0	0	0	0.00
Human Labour (Man Hrs.)	245.43	0.562	0.042	13.386	2.272	-0.75
Animal Labour (Pair Hrs.)	34.94	0.081	0.013	6.165	0.0002	-18.94*
Machine (Hrs.)	7.24	0.025	0.005	4.636	0.003	7.54*
Irrigation Machine (Hrs.)	16.98	0.051	0.053	0.957	0.351	34.26
Insecticides (real price)	450.00	0.009	0.002	4.225	0.0008	35.78*

Compound annual growth in price of output of gram in Chhattisgarh during 2002-03 to 2017-18

The average price received of gram by the farmer's of Chhattisgarh over 2002-03 to 2017-18 was 2461.91 rupees per quintal and compound annual growth rate was 8.22%

Table 2 Compound annual growth in price of output of gram in Chhattisgarh during 2002-03 to 2017-18

Year	Price/ qu
2002-03	1248.12
2003-04	1301.17

2004-05	1396.09
2005-06	1728.53
2006-07	1985.29
2007-08	2192.03
2008-09	1893.43
2009-10	1937.13
2010-11	1967.63
2011-12	2636.36
2012-13	3043.99
2013-14	2561.80
2014-15	3050.86
2015-16	4309.00
2016-17	4776.38
2017-18	3363.08
average	2461.93

growth rate 8.22

Total Input, Total Output and Total factor productivity indices of Gram in Chhattisgarh State during 2002-03 to 2017-18

The Total Factor Productivity (TFP) in Gram, Chhattisgarh, which measures the overall efficiency and productivity of the production process, showed variations over the years from 2002-03 to 2017-18. 2002-03 was base year which was 100, out put index gradually increased to reach its highest point of 179.99 in 2017-18. The Input Index, representing the input factors used in production, also experienced variations. It ranged from a low of 86.10 in 2009-10 to a high of 106.38 in 2017-18. TFP, which reflects the overall efficiency and productivity of the production process, exhibited fluctuations as well, with a peak value of 195.97 in 2012-13 and a low of 126.14 in 2003-04. the average Output Index stands at 147.53, the average Input Index at 94.95, and the average TFP at 155.67, indicating the overall performance of the Gram in Chhattisgarh during the given period.

Table 3. Total Input, Total Output and Total factor productivity indices of Gram in Chhattisgarh State during 2002-03 to 2017-18

Obsn	Output Index	Input Index	TFP
2002-03	100.00	100.00	100.00
2003-04	125.09	99.17	126.14
2004-05	125.76	97.63	128.82
2005-06	141.37	96.35	146.72
2006-07	146.50	100.49	145.79
2007-08	150.96	95.35	158.32
2008-09	125.56	86.20	145.65
2009-10	124.62	86.10	144.75
2010-11	135.77	89.13	152.32
2011-12	155.05	92.63	167.39
2012-13	172.11	87.83	195.97
2013-14	158.99	92.70	171.52
2014-15	175.01	95.46	183.34
2015-16	165.27	95.70	172.69
2016-17	178.43	98.01	182.06
2017-18	179.99	106.38	169.19
mean	147.53	94.95	155.67

Fig 1. Total Input, Total Output and Total factor productivity indices of Gram in Chhattisgarh State during 2002-03 to 2017-18

Compound growth rate of input, output and TFP indices of the major crops in Chhattisgarh states in 2002-03 to 2017-18 Table 4. showed the compound growth rate of total factor productivity estimated to quantify the contributions of various factors to TFP index growth such as seed, manure, fertilizer, insecticide, irrigation charges, machine labour, animal labour and land cost on

TFP index. in Chhattisgarh state, the growth of TFP index gram was 4.66% and significant at 10 per cent level of probability. The growth of output index was found to be positive gram 0.67 and non

significant. In input index growth rate was observed gram 1.71% and found to be significant at 1 cent level of probability.

Table 4. Compound growth rate of input, output and TFP indices of the major crops in Chhattisgarh states in 2002-03 to 2017-18

Reg. Coef. (b)	Input Index (%)	Reg. Coef. (b)	Output Index (%)	Reg. Coef. (b)	TFP (%)
0.0060	0.6700	0.0130	1.27*	0.0652	4.66***

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